

Growing Stock Volume Map to support forest operation planning

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1. General presentation of the GO-SURF operational group

The GO-SURF Operational Group (Figure 1) for “Decision Support System for Sustainable Forest Planning” took place in the Tuscany Region between 2019 and 2022, under the coordination of the Italian Academy of Forest Sciences. It led to the formalization of a broad partnership agreement bringing together the most important research organizations in the forestry sector operating in the territory of the Tuscany Region, in collaboration with the various players in the forest-wood supply chain and the various services associated with it. The consortium partners are : the Italian Academy of Forest Sciences, the Department of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Forestry (DAGRI) of the University of Florence, Studio Déméter, I Pini (Cooperative Agricultural Society - Producers' Organization), Rimorini Wood, Alma Cérés, CREA (Council for Agricultural Research and Analysis of the Agricultural Economy), CNR (National Research Council, Institute of Biometeorology), DREAM Italy, the RDM project, and the Foresters' Company. GO-SURF aims to create a decision support system (DSS) applied to the entire Tuscany region, based on spatial modeling, to support sustainable forest management on a company-wide scale. This tool aims to increase the area of forest managed sustainably, as well as helping to develop more effective forest planning.

Figure 1. Logotype of the GO-SURF Operational group.

2. A specific innovation of the GO-SURF operational group: the development and digital integration of Growing Stock Volume Map

Growing Stock Volume Maps (m³/ha) provide information of the most important forest variables for foresters since it is of high relevance in the planning and economic evaluation of forestry operations, as well as in the implementation of a forest management plan.

In fact, the Growing Stock Volume maps enable the forest managers to : - precisely quantify the wood resources available in a specific area, in order to assess the sustainability of the intervention; - prioritize the areas and silvicultural work to be carried out with regard to the quantity of wood available; - sustainably plan interventions to respect the forest cycle, avoiding over-exploitation and promoting natural regeneration; - Support biodiversity, by orienting interventions towards more environmentally-friendly practices; - Monitor changes in stand structure over time, and evaluate the effectiveness of silvicultural practices carried out.

2.1 Methodology used to produce growing stock volume maps

In the context of the GO-SURF operational group, two different types of Growing Stock Volume map were derived. One for the entire Tuscany Region, and one for specific area where forest management plan are conducted by the company involved in the GO-SURF partnership. In details, the data of field plot of the national and local forest inventory were used in conjunction with Remote Sensing and Auxiliary data from which predictors variables were used to apply the area-based approach (Chirici et al., 2020).

2.1.1. Details of remote sensing data used

In details, predictors from Sentinel-2 satellites imagery was used for the development of the Regional Growing Stock Map. Sentinel-2 satellites (A and B) are part of the European Space Agency's Copernicus program and are equipped with multispectral sensors that provide data in 13 spectral bands, from the visible spectrum to short-wave infrared, enabling the monitoring of various environmental variables, including forest cover and vegetation health. This data can be used to detect changes in vegetation structure, but also to extract multiple predictors variables for biomass estimation.

The advantages of Sentinel-2 satellites are: high spatial resolution (down to 10 meters), providing detailed observations of forest structure; a 5-day revisit frequency (at the equator), contributing to continuous monitoring of forest dynamics; data in 13 spectral bands, enabling the extraction of numerous predictive variables and a wide range of vegetation indices (such as NDVI), to assess forest biomass, health and productivity; and finally, free and open access to these data.

For developing the growing stock map at local scale (i.e. management plan scale), photogrammetric data acquired by drone were used to extract predictors based also on 3D data such as Digital Surface Model and Canopy Height Model.

2.1.2 Area-based approach to quantify Growing Stock Volume

The area-based approach (ABA) is a widely used method that combines LiDAR/Satellite and Photogrammetric data and field plot measurements to estimate stand characteristics such as growing stock volume. This approach takes advantage of the strengths of both data sources: the spatial coverage and predictive variables extracted from remote sensing data, on the one hand, and the accuracy and specificity of field plots, on the other. This approach reduces the number of plots to be surveyed in the field.

2.1.2.1 Field plot acquisition

In the GO-SURF operational group, for the development of the Growing Stock Volume Map at Regional Level the National Forest Inventory Plot of 2005 were used, while for the forest management plan scale growing stock volume map 25 circular plot of 530 m² were placed based on a stratified sampling design to take into account the variability of forest conditions within the area (Figure 2). For each plot, detailed measurements were collected, including tree diameter at breast height (DBH), tree height, tree species and density, and the GPS position of the plot center. These measurements are then used to calculate standing timber volume at plot level.

Figure 2 : Presentation of the pilot areas of the project in the Tuscany region.

2.1.2.2 Sentinel-2 predictor variable extraction and canopy height model (CHM)

Various predictive variables were extracted on the basis of the remote sensing data mentioned above. These include spectral band values and vegetation indices from the Sentinel-2 satellites, as well as tree heights from the canopy height model of photogrammetric data.

2.1.2.3 Statistical modeling

Field plot measurements are then linked to predictor variables, using regression models or machine learning algorithms. Within the GO-SURF operational group, the following common approaches have been used: - Linear regression models; - “Random Forest” or other machine learning methods for complex relationships.

These models were used to predict growing stock volume over the entire study area from the predictor variables, with a spatial resolution of 23m x 23m.

2.1.2.4 Mapping Growing Stock Volume

Once the model had been calibrated, it was applied to the data set of predictors to generate spatially explicit maps of standing timber volume (Figure 3). These maps provide continuous estimates of growing stock volume for the entire forest area under consideration.

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The way in which data is queried within the platform has been designed in collaboration with stakeholders (farmers, forest owners and managers, and forestry companies), to ensure that it meets their needs. Querying Growing Stock Volume Maps directly via the platform facilitates the extraction of relevant reports and geographical data, rationalizing decision-making processes and improving overall forest management practices.

Figure 3. Presentation of three maps of standing timber volumes (m³/ha) for three of the demonstration sites: Marina di Grosseto, Rincine and Vallombrosa.

2.2 Integrating growing stock volume maps into a digital decision support system (DSS)

The resulting maps are then easily accessible online, via a decision support system integrated into a digital platform (<https://go-surf.app/en/#/it>), enabling users to interrogate the data using interactive tools such as drawing or polygon upload (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Presentation of the decision-support platform that has been developed, giving forestry players access to growing stock volume maps.

3. Conclusions

As part of the GO-SURF project, the use of forest resource maps has proved to be a valuable tool for optimizing silvicultural operations. These maps, which detail the distribution and volume of wood resources, enable forest managers to plan operations with greater precision, thus ensuring effective sustainable management.

By integrating detailed spatial data, these maps help identify areas requiring specific interventions, such as thinning, selective cutting or regeneration treatments. In this way, activities can be prioritized and adapted to actual needs, to promote ecological balance, improve forest health and reduce unnecessary disturbance.

In addition to guiding silvicultural practices, these resource maps are an essential element in the creation of wood assortment maps (wood type, quality and potential end use), and enable the harvesting process to be planned according to needs.

By combining resource maps with wood assortment maps, stakeholders can accurately estimate the economic income from planned interventions, and thus the economic potential of the forest.

Information on the volume and quality of harvestable wood helps to forecast income, carry out cost-benefit analyses and, finally, assess the long-term sustainability of financial gains while maintaining forest productivity and health.

This dual use of maps - both for planning silvicultural interventions and for assessing economic benefits - makes them indispensable for achieving sustainable forest management in modern forestry.

Access to maps via the decision support system platform can also bring a number of benefits to the forestry sector in the Tuscany region, particularly in small forest holdings which are generally abandoned. In this sense, the platform can be used in the coming years to develop efficient and sustainable wood mobilization practices while minimizing environmental impacts. The maps can also be used to build new timber value chains, which are not always well organized in Tuscany's forestry sectors.

Bibliography

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Further information

- <https://www.innovarurale.it/it/pei-agri/gruppi-operativi/bancadati-go-pei/supporto-decisionale-alla-pianificazione-forestale>
- <https://youtu.be/tIyNjOTKPY>
- Website: <https://www.go-surf.it/>

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